

EBFMC25-OP-85 · Burnout Levels and Associated Factors Among Physicians in Türkiye: A Questionnaire Based Study

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AUTHORS

Mehmet Yildiz
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0706-0906>

Muhammet Rasit Aydin
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4202-0099>

Abdulkadir Aydin
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0663-586X>

AFFILIATIONS

Giresun Bulancak No. 2 Sht. Er Enver Erdogan
Family Health Center
Giresun, Turkey

Sakarya University
Faculty of Medicine
Sakarya, Turkey

Sakarya University
Faculty of Medicine
Sakarya, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Physicians face a high risk of burnout due to heavy workloads, long hours, and high responsibility (West, Dyrbye, & Shanafelt, 2018). Burnout consists of three components: emotional exhaustion (EE), depersonalization (DP) and reduced personal accomplishment (PA) (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). This study aims to determine burnout levels among physicians in Türkiye and examine the demographic, occupational and environmental factors associated with burnout (Günay & Taşkaya, 2013).

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted among physicians in Türkiye. The sample was selected randomly and participants completed a survey including demographic data, researcher-prepared questions and the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) (Ergin, 1992). Data were analyzed using SPSS, with burnout-related factors assessed via chi-square tests, t-tests, and logistic regression.

Results: Between February 01, 2024, and June 20, 2024, 1312 physicians completed the survey, representing all regions of Türkiye. A significant proportion of physicians reported moderate to high burnout. Physicians experienced moderate EE and DP but had high PA scores. Nearly half had high EE levels, while DP and PA remained moderate. Factors associated with EE and DP included age, marital status, parenthood, years in practice, sector, legal cases, administrative duties, exposure to violence, and patient load. Additionally, job dissatisfaction, shift work, workplace conditions, support from healthcare staff, and perceived income affected both EE and DP as well as PA.

Conclusion: Burnout is a widespread problem among physicians in Türkiye, impacting professional performance, patient care quality, and healthcare system sustainability (Shanafelt et al., 2012). Addressing burnout requires improving working conditions, enhancing support systems and balancing workloads (West et al., 2018). Physicians with lower burnout and higher job satisfaction contribute to a more effective healthcare system. Preventing burnout strengthens physician-patient relationships and improves healthcare quality. A sustainable approach should focus on both individual and institutional strategies to support physicians and enhance system efficiency.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Burnout, burnout professional, physicians

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Mehmet Yildiz

Giresun Bulancak No. 2 Sht. Er Enver Erdogan

Family Health Center

Giresun, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0706-0906>

drmehmetyildiz54@gmail.com